

Report
On
“THE SCIENCE BEHIND TRADITIONAL PRACTICES”

Submitted by
ANSARI FAIZAN

Roll No: 01
B. Pharm: Final Year

Project Guide
Mr.Imran Wahab

Maulana Azad Education Trust's
Y. B. Chavan College of Pharmacy
Dr. Rafiq Zakaria Campus
Aurangabad- 431001.

2019-2020

Dr. Rafiq Zakaria Campus

Maulana Azad Educational Trust's

Y.B. Chavan College of Pharmacy

Dr. Rafiq Zakaria Marg, Rauza Bagh, Aurangabad

C E R T I F I C A T E

This is to certify that the project titled “THE SCIENCE BEHIND TRADITIONAL PRACTICES” represent the bonafide work of **MR. ANSARI FAIZAN** submitted as Library assignment for the Degree of Bachelor of Pharmacy. This work has been carried out in the Y.B. Chavan College of Pharmacy, affiliated to Dr.Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad under the supervision and guidance of **Mr.Imran Wahab**.

Date:

Dr.ZahidZaheer

Place: Aurangabad

Principal

Dr. Rafiq Zakaria Campus

Maulana Azad Educational Trust's

Y.B. Chavan College of Pharmacy

Dr. Rafiq Zakaria Marg, Rauza Bagh, Aurangabad

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project titled “THE SCIENCE BEHIND TRADITIONAL PRACTICES” represent the bonafide work of **Mr. Ansari Faizan** submitted as Library assignment for the Degree of Bachelor of Pharmacy. This work has been carried out in the Y.B. Chavan College of Pharmacy, affiliated to Dr.Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad, under my supervision and guidance.

Date:
Wahab

Mr.Imran

Declaration

I, the undersigned **Mr. Ansari Faizan** of B.Pharm Final Year of Y. B. Chavan College of Pharmacy, hereby declare that the project work entitled “**THE SCIENCE BEHIND TRADITIONAL PRACTICES**” has been carried out by me under the supervision and guidance of **Mr.Imran Wahab**. Y. B. Chavan College of Pharmacy affiliated to Dr. Baba saheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad during 2019-20. The contents present in the project are my own original research contribution and the same are not submitted to any other institute or university for award of any degree or diploma.

Date:

Place: Aurangabad

MR. ANSARI FAIZAN

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to thank all those who helped me directly or indirectly in successful completion of this project work. Thanking to all of them individually would make the task easy, although I must make special thanks to some of the personalities.

I feel deeply obliged and indebted to **Mrs. Fatma Rafiq Zakaria**, Honorable Chairman, Maulana Azad Educational Trust, for providing us state of the art facilities required for healthy working environment and facilitating the learning process.

I would like to acknowledge the ever helping, highly eminent and respectable **Dr. Zahid Zaheer, Principal** for creating such encouraging atmosphere due to which the project work has been possible.

Words seem insufficient to express my deep sense of gratitude to my highly esteemed and respectable guide: **Mr. Imran Wahab** for his/her scholarly insights, logical thinking, valuable guidance, innovative ideas and constant inspiration.

The various information and sources I used during my report completion find place in my project

DATE:

PLACE: Aurangabad

ANSARI FAIZAN

INDEX

Sr. No.	Content	Page no
1	Introduction	
2	Lemon	
2	Black Tea	
4	Black Tea with Lemon	
5	Chew pan or Betel leaves	
6	Ginger	
7	Orange	
8	Papaya	
9	Carrot	
10	Bitter Gourd (Karela)	
11	Dates	
12	Apple	
13	Turmeric	
14	References	

Introduction

Traditional practices are nothing but the home remedies or our day to day life activities. As we know we are using allopathy system of medicine for the treatment of various diseases but we also know that this system of medicine produces various side effects with their uses. We are eating vegetables" fruits and other substances in our day to day life activities this substances are also used for the treatment of various diseases there for we need to utilize this practices as much as possible in our day to day life to treat the diseases and to avoid various side effects. The WHO notes, however, that "inappropriate use of traditional medicines or practices can have negative or dangerous effects" and that "further research is needed to ascertain the efficacy and safety" of several of the practices and medicinal plants used by traditional medicine systems. The line between alternative medicine and quackery is a contentious subject. Traditional practices used effectively in the treatment of a wide range of ailments. They are able to offer treatment if they are used correctly and regularly. They are also very often derived from natural sources and holistic health. One of the best advantages of home remedies is the number of illnesses and health conditions in which they can treat. Some of the common ailments that can be treated and cured.

Lemon

Content:

Lemons are loaded with pectin fibers that prevent hunger pangs thus cutting down junk food intake. Lemon juice is a powerhouse of essential vitamins and minerals including vitamin C, E and A, calcium, magnesium and iron. The alkaline property of lemon juice maintains a healthy pH level within the body which in turn prevents fat storage. Lemons contain a compound called polyphenol that help in weight loss. Drinking a glass of lemon water everyday helps to flush out toxins from the body, enhances proper functioning of the vital organs including liver and kidney as well as boost the immunity systems.

Nutrition and Phytochemicals:

Lemon is a rich source of vitamin C, providing 64% of the Daily Value in a 100 g reference amount (table). Other essential nutrients are low in content.

Lemons contain numerous phytochemicals, including polyphenols, terpenes, and tannins. Lemon juice contains slightly more citric acid than lime juice (about 47 g/l), nearly twice the citric acid of grapefruit juice, and about five times the amount of citric acid found in orange juice.

Uses

High Blood Pressure: Lemon contains potassium which controls high blood pressure and reduces the effect of nausea and dizziness.

Prevent Cauliflower From Turning Brown: Cauliflower tend to turn brown with even the slightest cooking. You can make sure the white vegetables stay white by squeezing a teaspoon of fresh lemon juice on them before heating.

Mental Health:

Lemon water can also prep up your mood and relieve you from depression and stress. Long distance walkers and world travelers as well as explorers look upon the lemon as a Godsend. When fatigue begins, a lemon is sucked through a hole in the top. Quick acting medicine it is, giving almost unbelievable refreshments.

Respiratory Problem:

Lemon water can reduce phlegm; and can also help you breathe properly and aids a person suffering with asthma.

a)Treating Arthritis and Rheumatism:

Lemon is a diuretic - assists in the production of urine which helps you to reduce inflammation by flushing out toxins and bacteria while also giving you relief from arthritis and rheumatism.

b)Prevents Kidney Stones:

Regular consumption of the refreshing drink -- or even lemon juice mixed with water -- may increase the production of urinary citrate, a chemical in the urine that prevent the formation of crystals that may build up into kidney stones.

c)Keep Insects Out of the Kitchen:

You don't need insecticides or ant traps to ant-proof your kitchen. Just give it the lemon treatment. First squirt some lemon juice on door.

d)Anti-Aging:

Lemon water reduces the production of free radicals which are responsible for aging skin and skin damage. Lemon water is calorie free and an antioxidant.

Oral Health:

Lemon juice also stops bleeding gums and reduces toothaches.

Stomach Health:

Digestive problems are the most common ailments but warm water and lime juice is the solution to most digestive problems. Lemon juice helps to purify the blood, reduces your chances of indigestion, constipation, eliminates toxins from the body, adds digestion and reduces phlegm.

Black tea

Introduction:

Black tea is a type of tea that is more oxidized than oolong, green, and white teas. Black tea is generally stronger in flavour than the less oxidized teas. All four types are made from leaves of the shrub (or small tree) *Camellia sinensis*. Two principal varieties of the species are used – the small-leaved Chinese variety plant (*C. sinensis* var. *sinensis*), used for most other types of teas, and the large-leaved Assamese plant (*C. sinensis* var. *assamica*), which was traditionally mainly used for black tea, although in recent years some green and white teas have been produced. In China, where black tea was discovered, the beverage is called "red tea" due to the color of the oxidized leaves when processed appropriately.^[1]

Content:

Black tea (just like green tea) is plucked from a plant called *Camellia sinensis*. The leaves of black tea, are steeped such that it can give a dark colour when used as a beverage. Also, the leaves are mature dry and processed such that it has a dark colour. Black tea has extremely low caffeine content, which is great for circulation.

Fluoride is another content of black tea and thus allows oral and bone health. Black tea, contains flavonoids which are also found in apples. Unlike green tea, black tea, once processed eliminates all antioxidants existing in it. Black tea not only helps to fight bacteria but also strengthens the immune system. As one knows, drinking tea hydrates the body, thus a cup of black tea helps moisturise the skin. Black tea also balances the hormone levels, which fends off stress. Not only does black tea have anti-inflammatory qualities, it also keeps a check on the digestive tracts functioning. It can help reduce stroke risks as it balances the cholesterol level.

Benefits of black tea:

Oral Health:

Studies funded by the Tea Trade Health Research Association suggests that black tea reduces plaque formation as well as restricts bacteria growth that promotes the formation of cavities and tooth decays. Polyphenols found in black tea kill and surpass cavity-causing bacteria as well as hinder the growth of bacterial enzymes that form the sticky-like material that binds plaque to our teeth.

A Better Heart:

As identified by Arab L. et al. in their 2009 research paper called "Green and black tea consumption and risk of stroke: a meta-analysis", it is seen that regardless of people's country of origin, individuals who consume 3 or more cups of tea had a 21% lower risk of a stroke than people who consume less than 1 cup of green or black tea per day

Antioxidants:

Black tea contains polyphenols, which are also antioxidants that help block DNA damage associated with tobacco or other toxic chemicals. These antioxidants are different from those obtained from fruits and vegetables and therefore as a regular part of our diet they can provide additional benefits towards a healthy lifestyle.

Cancer Prevention:

Though a lot more research is required to confidently suggest cancer prevention techniques, some research over the years suggests that antioxidants like polyphenol and catechins in tea may help prevent some types of cancer. It has been suggested that women who drink black tea regularly have a lower chance of ovarian cancer than their counterparts.

Healthy Bones:

It has also been suggested that regular tea drinkers have stronger bones and lower probability of developing arthritis due to the phytochemicals found in tea.

Lower Risk of Diabetes:

Based on a research study conducted of elderly people living in the Mediterranean islands it was discovered that people that had been consuming black tea on a long-term basis on a moderate level (i.e 1-2 cups a day) had a 70% lower chance of having or developing type 2 diabetes.

Stress Relief:

We all are aware and well experienced about the calming and relaxing benefits of black tea. Not only does it help slow you down after a long day, studies show that the amino acid L-thiamine found in black tea can help you relax and concentrate better. Black tea has also been shown to reduce levels of the stress hormone cortisol when consumed in moderate amounts on a regular basis.

Better Immune System:

Black tea contains alkyl amine antigens that help boost our immune response. In addition it also contains tannins that have the ability to fight viruses and hence keep us protected from influenza, stomach flu and other such commonly found viruses in our everyday lives.

Healthy Digestive Tract:

In addition to improving your immune system, tannins also have a therapeutic effect on gastric and intestinal illnesses and also help decrease digestive activity.

Black tea with Lemon

Content:

Black tea is a calorie-free beverage that contains caffeine and can help lower the risk of stroke and heart disease. These benefits may come from tea's theaflavin antioxidants, which can also help prevent certain forms of cancer. Tea is traditionally made with a sweetener and milk, which increases its sugar and caloric content. However, by replacing sugar and milk with a citrus fruit, such as lemon, you can increase health-boosting and nutritional potential of tea.

Uses of black tea with lemon

Nutritional Powerhouse:

Lemons are a rich source of vitamin C -- 1 cup of lemon juice provides more than the daily recommended dose. The ascorbic acid in vitamin C acts as an antioxidant that helps fight free radicals, which can cause heart disease and diabetes. Lemons are also a good source of minerals and vitamins, including folate, potassium, magnesium and thiamine. Adding it to black tea doesn't inhibit its nutritional effects, which makes the combination ideal for consumption.

Add Lemon, Not Milk

Common additions to tea such as milk can block the potential health benefits of its antioxidants. A small German study, published in a 2007 issue of the "European Heart Journal," determined that

the caseins found in milk reduced the effects of the antioxidants. Milk binds with the antioxidants found in black tea, which prevents them from being absorbed, explains MedlinePlus. However, not all studies confirm milk inhibits black tea's antioxidants, and more research is required. Lemon makes milk curdle, which helps you avoid adding milk to your tea. Without milk, lemon seems to maximize the health benefits of drinking black tea.

Lower Calories

Adding sugar or whipped cream turns calorie-free black tea into a high-calorie beverage. Lemon's naturally occurring sugars make it a suitable replacement to artificial sweeteners without the high increase in calories. Lemon also improves the taste due to its natural sugar content and citrus flavor. Replacing sugar and other fattening foods with lemons helps you reduce your calorie intake.

Antioxidants Staying Power:

Other than providing an additional source of antioxidants, lemons also increase the staying power of antioxidants in black tea. Black tea contains theaflavins, which are polyphenol antioxidants similar to those found in green tea. They have the potential to reduce the risk of Parkinson's disease, heart attacks, hardening of the arteries and kidney

Stones. In a comparative study published in a 2000 issue of "Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology," researchers found that tea with lemon increased its antioxidants potential more than tea without milk.

Chew pan or Betel leaves

Content:

Chewing paan aka betel quid is widely considered a bad habit. While people believe that chewing paan is extremely harmful, let us tell you that the infamous betel leaf mouth freshener has many health benefits. Paan which is often made with catechu (katha), areca nut (supari) and tobacco (zarda) is chewed after meals. With tobacco it becomes harmful

and people often get addicted to it. This can lead to acute diseases like oral or stomach cancer.

Ideally, a paan is made by wrapping areca nut, tobacco and slaked lime in betel leaf. Since tobacco and areca nuts are known to cause cancer, chewing paan with them should be avoided. The betel leaf has many medicinal benefits and has been extensively used in Ayurveda.

Have a look at the many health benefits of chewing paan:

Improves digestion:

Chewing betel leaves takes a lot of effort and „works“ your salivary gland. It stimulates the release of saliva which is the first step of digestion, as various enzymes in it break down food, making it easy to digest. Natural substances like ginger, figs, fennel etc. are also known to improve digestion.

Carcinogenesis in the oral cavity:

Chewing betel leaves has also shown to prevent oral cancer by maintaining the levels of ascorbic acid in the saliva .Ascorbic acid is an excellent antioxidant, which helps reduce the free radicals in the body, thus preventing cancer.

Helps maintain good oral hygiene:

Betel leaves have various compounds which have bactericidal effects that help in destroying bad breath causing bacteria. Also, various spices like cloves, fennel, and cardamom. etc. when wrapped in betel nut to make paan, make an excellent mouth-freshener. Spices like cloves, cinnamon, nutmeg etc. are also known to solve many oral problems.

Is an aphrodisiac:

Betel leaf is known to have aphrodisiac properties and chewing paan right before having sex makes the process more enjoyable. It is a common practice to offer *masala* paan to newlyweds.

Treats gastric ulcers :

Extracts of betel leaves are known to have gastro protective activity and help in preventing gastric ulcers.

Treatment of warts:

Betel leaves are a major component in various Ayurvedic medicines used in treating warts. These medicines are known to not leave any scarring and remove the wart completely without recurrence.

Treats diabetes:

Extracts of betel leaves are known to control blood sugar levels and have an effective anti-diabetic property. 4

Treats cough:

Betel leaf extract mixed with honey is known to relieve cough and helps removing phlegm from the chest.

Relieves headache :

Betel leaf is also known to have analgesic properties and hence applying it over the affected area is known to effectively reduce headache.

Heals wounds:

Juice of betel leaves, when applied over a wound and bandaged with betel leaves is known to heal within two days.

Cures constipation :

Stalk of betel leaves dipped in castor oil, when introduced in the rectum, effectively relieves constipation. Along with betel leaves, natural remedies like flaxseeds, triphala, lemon, etc. are also known to cure constipation.

Y.B CHAVAN COLLEGE OF PHARMACY AURANGABAD.43100

Ginger

Scientific Name(s):

Zingiber officinale Roscoe; occasionally Zingiber, capitatum Smith. Family: Zingiberaceae.

Common Name(s):

Ginger, ginger root, black ginger, zingiberis rhizoma

Constituents:

Only unbleached ginger (scraped or unscraped) is accepted as a medicinal-grade drug, containing 1.5% or more volatile oil. Quality standards for ginger can be found in the United States Pharmacopeia National Formulary.

Over 400 different compounds have been identified in ginger. The major constituents in ginger rhizomes are carbohydrates (50% to 70%), which are present as starch. The concentration of lipids is 3% to 8% and includes free fatty acids (eg, palmitic, oleic, linoleic, linolenic, capric, lauric, myristic), triglycerides, and lecithins. Oleoresin provides 4% to 7.5% of pungent substances as gingerol homologues, shogaol homologues, zingerone, and volatile oils. Volatile oils are present in 1% to 3% concentrations and consist mainly of the sesquiterpenes, beta-bisabolene, and zingiberene; other sesquiterpenes include zingiberol and zingiberenol. Numerous monoterpenes

are also present. Amino acids, raw fiber, ash, protein, phytosterols, vitamins (eg, nicotinic acid and vitamin A), and minerals are among the other constituents. Analyses of the oleoresins have resulted in the identification of a class of structurally related compounds called gingerols, which form shogaols and degrade further to zingerone when dehydrated. The main components are [6]-gingerol and [6]-shogaol; however, the pharmacologically active compounds [6]- and [10]-dehydrogingerdione and [6]- and [10]-gingerdione have also been identified.

Uses:

There are many traditional uses for ginger, but more recent interest in the use of ginger centers on the prevention and management of nausea. Ginger may play a role in osteoarthritic pain and cancer. However, there is limited clinical information to support these uses.

Cancer

Antitumor activity of ginger and its constituents has been demonstrated in several in vitro and animal experiments. Apoptotic cell death and antiproliferative effects caused by gingerol, paradol, shogaol, essential oil of ginger, and dried homogenized ginger have been demonstrated in mice and human cell lines. No human trials with the use of ginger in cancer have been published.

Chemotherapy-related nausea

A trend toward effectiveness has been demonstrated in a limited number of trials in chemotherapy-related nausea, whereas others have found no effect with the addition of ginger to standard antiemetic regimens. A case report describes a reduction in disequilibrium and nausea associated with abrupt discontinuation or intermittent noncompliance with selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (1 g of ginger given 3 times daily).

Motion sickness

Results from the limited published studies are equivocal, with 3 of 7 trials reporting ginger root effective as a preventative or in treatment. The remaining 4 trials found no benefit over the comparator/placebo. Doses ranged from 250 mg to 2 g in 1 trial, with no greater effectiveness for 2 g over the 1 g dose. ,

Postoperative nausea

Results from published trials and meta-analyses are equivocal. Limitations of meta-analyses include the lack of comparators, the heterogeneous study populations, and surgical procedures. In a meta-analysis of 5 randomized clinical trials investigating the efficacy of ginger in postoperative nausea, 1 g of ginger was more effective than placebo (relative risk, 0.69; confidence interval, 0.54 to 0.89). Other reviews and meta-analyses (some including trials excluded by others) did not find ginger useful in the postoperative setting; the numbers needed for effect range from 11 to 25.

Pregnancy-related nausea

In a Cochrane meta-analysis, only 1 trial using ginger met inclusion criteria. The majority of women in this crossover trial (n = 70) preferred using ginger to placebo. A 2005 review of 6 quality trials found ginger to be superior to placebo in 4 trials and comparable with vitamin B6 in 2 trials. Little information on fetal outcomes has been published in relation to clinical trials investigating the use of ginger in pregnancy.

Inhibition of platelet aggregation

Studies from animal models are inconclusive, but experiments with different ginger extracts have suggested an antiaggregation effect. Results in human experiments are equally inconclusive. Ginger has demonstrated an inhibitory effect as well as no effect on platelet aggregation at recommended daily doses (less than 5 g).

Osteoarthritis

Trials exploring the anti-inflammatory and pain-relieving effects of ginger have provided mixed results, with the majority of trials showing a trend toward pain relief greater than placebo but less than traditional anti-inflammatory drugs. Several trials have methodological flaws, including sponsorship by ginger-manufacturing companies. Mechanisms of action have been proposed and include inhibition of prostaglandin and leukotriene synthesis.

Other uses

Other actions of ginger and its constituents include cardiotoxic/toxic effects, effects on the CNS, enhanced testosterone production, and inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis. However, human studies are lacking.

Orange

Health Benefits of Oranges:

Oranges contain phytochemicals that protect against cancer

Oranges are rich in citrus limonoids, proven to help fight a number of varieties of cancer including that of the skin, lung, breast, stomach and colon

Orange juice can help prevent kidney diseases

Drinking orange juice regularly prevents kidney diseases and reduces the risk of kidney stones.

Note: drink juice in moderate amounts. The high sugar content of fruit juices can cause tooth decay and the high acid content can wear away enamel if consumed in excess.

Mandarin oranges fight liver cancer, according to studies.

According to two studies in Japan eating mandarin oranges reduces liver cancer. This may be due in part to vitamin A compounds known as carotenoids.

Oranges lower cholesterol

Since they're full of soluble fiber, oranges are helpful in lowering cholesterol.

They are rich in potassium and boost heart health.

Oranges are full of potassium, an electrolyte mineral responsible for helping the heart function well. When potassium levels get too low, you may develop an abnormal heart rhythm, known as an arrhythmia.

They lower the risk of diseases.

Oranges are full of vitamin C, which protects cells by neutralizing free radicals. Free radicals cause chronic diseases, like cancer and heart disease.

Oranges fight against viral infections.

Studies show that the abundance of polyphenols in oranges protects against viral infections.

They relieve constipation.

Oranges are full of dietary fiber which stimulates digestive juices and relieves constipation.

They aid in good eye health and protect vision.

Oranges are rich in carotenoid compounds which are converted to vitamin A and help prevent macular degeneration.

They regulate high blood pressure.

The flavonoid hesperidin found in oranges helps regulate high blood pressure and the magnesium in oranges helps maintain blood pressure.

Oranges alkalize the body.

Although oranges are acidic before you digest them, they contain many alkaline minerals that help to balance out the body after they are digested. In this respect, they are similar to lemons, which are one of the most alkaline foods available.

Oranges provide smart carbs and do not cause a blood sugar spike.

Oranges like all fruits have simple sugars in them, but the orange has a glycemic index of

Anything under 55 is considered low. This means as long as you don't eat too many oranges at one time, they won't spike your blood sugar and cause problems with insulin or weight gain.

Oranges have a wealth of nutrients including vitamin C, vitamin A precursors, calcium, potassium and pectin.

Papaya-

Nutritional break down of papaya:

One medium papaya has approximately 120 calories, 30 grams of carbohydrate (including 5 grams of fiber and 18 grams of sugar) and 2 grams of protein.

Papayas are an excellent source of vitamin C and one single medium fruit provides 224% of your daily needs. Papayas are a good source of folate, vitamin A, magnesium, copper, pantothenic acid and fiber.³ They also have B vitamins, alpha and beta carotene, lutein and zeaxanthin, vitamin E, calcium, potassium, vitamin K and lycopene, the powerful antioxidant most commonly associated with tomatoes

Papayas grow in tropical climates and are also known as papaws or pawpaws. Their sweet taste, vibrant color and wide variety of health benefits are just a few reasons to add them to your diet.

The possible health benefits of consuming papaya include a reduced risk of heart disease, diabetes, cancer, aiding in digestion, improving blood glucose control in diabetics, lowering blood pressure, and improving wound healing.

Uses:

The risks for developing asthma are lower in people who consume a high amount of certain nutrients. One of these nutrients is beta-carotene, contained in foods like papaya, apricots, broccoli, cantaloupe, pumpkin and carrots.

Cancer:

Consumption of the powerful antioxidant beta-carotene (found in papayas) has been shown to have an inverse association with the development of colon cancer in the Japanese population.

Among younger men, diets rich in beta-carotene may play a protective role against prostate cancer, according to a study conducted by the Harvard School of Public Health's Department of Nutrition.

Bone health:

Low intakes of vitamin K have been associated with a higher risk for bone fracture. Adequate vitamin K consumption is important for good health, as it acts as a modifier of bone matrix proteins, improves calcium absorption and may reduce urinary excretion of calcium.

Diabetes:

Studies have shown that type 1 diabetics who consume high-fiber diets have lower blood glucose levels and type 2 diabetics may have improved blood sugar, lipids and insulin levels. One medium papaya provides about 4.7 grams of fiber.

The Dietary Guidelines for Americans recommends 21-25 g/day for women and 30-38 g/day for men.

Digestion:

Papayas contain an enzyme called papain that aids in digestion and can also be used as a meat tenderizer.

Papaya is also high in fiber and water content, both of which help to prevent constipation and promote regularity and a healthy digestive tract.

Heart disease:

The fiber, potassium and vitamin content in papaya all help to ward off heart disease. An increase in potassium intake along with a decrease in sodium intake is the most important dietary change that a person can make to reduce their risk of cardiovascular disease.

Inflammation:

The choline is a very important and versatile nutrient in papayas that aids our bodies in sleep, muscle movement, learning and memory. Choline also helps to maintain the structure of cellular membranes, aids in the transmission of nerve impulses, assists in the absorption of fat and reduces chronic inflammation.

Skin and healing:

When used topically, mashed papaya appears to be beneficial for promoting wound healing and preventing infection of burned areas. Researchers believe that the proteolytic enzymes chymopapain and papain in papaya are responsible for its beneficial effects.² Ointments containing the papain enzyme have also been used to treat decubitus ulcers or bedsores.

Papaya is also great for your hair because it contains vitamin A, a nutrient required for sebum production that keeps hair moisturized. Vitamin A is also necessary for the growth of all bodily tissues, including skin and hair.

Adequate intake of vitamin C, which papaya can provide, is needed for the building and maintenance of collagen, which provides structure to skin and hair.

Carrots

Content and Uses:

Beta carotene:

Carrots are a rich source of this powerful antioxidant, which, among other vital uses, can be converted into vitamin A in the body to help maintain healthy skin.

Digestion:

Carrots increase saliva and supply essential minerals, vitamins and enzymes that aid indigestion. Eating carrots regularly may help prevent gastric ulcers and other digestive disorders.

Alkaline elements:

Carrots are rich in alkaline elements, which purify and revitalize the blood while balancing the acid/alkaline ratio of the body.

Potassium:

Carrots are a good source of potassium, which can help maintain healthy sodium levels in the body, thereby helping to reduce elevated blood pressure levels.

Dental Health:

Carrots kill harmful germs in the mouth and help prevent tooth decay.

Wounds:

Raw or grated carrots can be used to help heal wounds, cuts and inflammation.

Phytonutrients:

Among the many beneficial phytochemicals that carrots contain is a phytonutrient called falcarinol, which may reduce the risk of colon cancer and help promote overall colon health.

Carotenoids:

Carrots are rich in carotenoids, which our bodies can use to help regulate blood sugar.

Fiber:

Carrots are high in soluble fiber, which may reduce cholesterol by binding the LDL form (the kind we don't want) and increasing the HDL form (the kind our body needs) to help reduce blood clots and prevent heart disease.

Eyes, hair, nails and more!

The nutrients in carrots can improve the health of your eyes, skin, hair, nails and more through helping to detoxify your system and build new cells.

There are plenty more reasons to enjoy these crunchy, sweet root vegetables, so reserve a spot in your garden plot for planting some, or pop down to the local market to pick up a bunch.

Karela (Bitter gourd)

Though it is bitter to taste, the juice of Karela (Bitter Gourd) is full of essential nutrients. Not only is it extremely nutritional, it is, in fact, considered a miraculous health drink. Karela juice has innumerable health benefits. It is an essential tonic for those who are diabetic. Not only patients, but in fact, everyone can get some or the other benefit out of this juice.

Karela is profoundly grown in Asian and sub-tropical climates. It makes an essential detoxifier and skin cleanser. Regular intake of this bitter herb helps boost the immune system while removing all unnecessary toxins. Bitter guard is considered a fruit as it has seeds. However, the most common usage of this fruit is as a vegetable, often used for cooking.

Karela Juice Benefits for Health:

Diabetes:

Bitter gourd has multiple health benefits. It is mostly consumed for triggering the blood sugar level. Diabetes is a common ailment that affects many people today. Regular intake of bitter

gourd juice helps prevent the rise of blood sugar levels. It also helps cure insulin resistance without taking any external medication.

Cancer:

If not detected at the right stage, cancer is almost an incurable disease. Karela juice benefits to prevent some particular types of cancer. It also helps trigger leukemic cancer cells effectively.

Antioxidant:

Karela juice is an excellent natural antioxidant. Antioxidant is essential for removing toxins from the body. At the same time, it helps to rejuvenate the body cells and prevents free radicals. The juice of karela is the finest tonic for those who are addicted to smoking. Taking karela juice helps to cleanse the nicotine layer from the system.

Asthma:

Asthma patients can highly benefit by having karela juice. It helps cure chronic cough and breathing problems by removing the sputum that accumulates within the lungs and the respiratory tract.

Skin:

Karela juice is excellent for the skin. It helps to remove the fine lines from the upper surface of the skin. Having this juice will also prevent premature ageing. It helps cure and purify blood from within the system.

HIV/AIDS:

Regular consumption of karela juice is best for triggering the condition of an HIV patient. Studies conducted on natural antidotes of HIV/AIDS establish the goodness of bitter guard in preventing further damaging of the skin cells.

Weight loss:

Bitter gourd is excellent for weight loss. Karela benefits to weight loss is attributed to its high fiber and low carbohydrates and calories content. It makes an ideal diet for those who are on a weight loss program.

Immune system:

Karela juice helps boost the immune system.

Constipation:

Regular consumption of karela helps to cure constipation

DATES:

Benefits of ates:

Lowers cholesterol:

Did you know that dates are free from cholesterol, and contain very little fat? Including them in smaller quantities in your daily diet can help you keep a check on cholesterol level, and even assist in weight loss.

Protein rich:

Dates are a strong source for proteins that help us in staying fit, and even keep our muscles strong. A lot of regular gym goers are asked to eat a couple of dates every day as part of their daily routine.

Rich in vitamins:

Dates contain vitamins such as B1, B2, B3 and B5, as well as A1 and C. If you have a few dates every day, you won't have to take vitamin supplements. Not only will it keep you healthy, there will be a noticeable change in your energy levels as well because dates contain natural sugars such as glucose, sucrose, and fructose, too. So it works really well as a quick snack.

Improves bone health:

Dates are rich in selenium, manganese, copper, and magnesium, and all of these are required when it comes to keeping our bones healthy, and preventing conditions such as osteoporosis.

Strengthens the nervous system:

Dates are loaded with potassium, and yet contain little sodium, and that goes a long way in keeping your nervous system in order. The potassium helps to reduce cholesterol, and keeps the risk of a stroke in check.

Rich in iron:

Apart from the fluorine that keeps your teeth healthy, dates also contain iron, which is highly recommended for those who suffer from iron deficiency. Plus it's great for blood purification as well.

Promotes digestion:

If you soak a few dates in water and chew on them daily, your digestive system will behave itself very well. Plus it's recommended for those who have trouble with constipation.

Improves skin:

The vitamins C and D work on your skin's elasticity, and also keep your skin

smooth. Plus, if you suffer from skin problems, incorporating dates into your diet might help you in the long run. Plus dates also come with anti-ageing benefits, and prevent the accumulation of melanin in your body.

Fixes hangovers:

While we haven't exactly tried it out, but it's said that dates are an excellent way to control inebriation. And similarly, it also helps to cure hangovers. But

for best results, you have to rub the skin a bit, and soak it in water overnight and then eat it.

Assists in weight gain:

The sugar, proteins, and other vitamins in the fruit help in weight gain, especially when you need it. Incidentally, it's said that when eaten with cucumber, dates help to keep your weight at a normal level. Now that's what we call flexibility

Apple

Benefits of eating apple:

Get whiter, healthier teeth

An apple won't replace your toothbrush, but biting and chewing an apple stimulates the production of saliva in your mouth, reducing tooth decay by lowering the levels of bacteria.

Avoid Alzheimer's

A new study performed on mice shows that drinking apple juice could keep Alzheimer's away and fight the effects of aging on the brain. Mice in the study that were fed an apple- enhanced diet showed higher levels of the neurotransmitter acetylcholine and did better in maze tests than those on a regular diet.

Protect against Parkinson's

Research has shown that people who eat fruits and other high-fibre foods gain a certain amount of protection against Parkinson's, a disease characterized by a breakdown of the brain's dopamine-producing nerve cells. Scientists have linked this to the free radical- fighting power of the antioxidants contained therein.

Decrease your risk of diabetes

Women who eat at least one apple a day are 28 percent less likely to develop type 2 diabetes than those who don't eat apples. Apples are loaded with soluble fibre, the key to blunting blood sugar swings.

Reduce cholesterol

The soluble fibre found in apples binds with fats in the intestine, which translates into lower cholesterol levels and a healthier you.

Get a healthier heart

An extensive body of research has linked high soluble fibre intake with a slower buildup of cholesterol-rich plaque in your arteries. The phenolic compound found in apple skins also prevents the cholesterol that gets into your system from solidifying on your artery walls. When plaque builds inside your arteries, it reduces blood flow to your heart, leading to coronary artery disease.

Prevent gallstones

Gallstones form when there's too much cholesterol in your bile for it to remain as a liquid, so it solidifies. They are particularly prevalent in the obese. To prevent gallstones, doctors recommend a diet high in fibre to help you control your weight and cholesterol levels.

Beat diarrhea and constipation

Whether you can't go to the bathroom or you just can't stop, fibre found in apples can help. Fibre can either pull water out of your colon to keep things moving along when you're backed up, or absorb excess water from your stool to slow your bowels down.

Neutralize irritable bowel syndrome

Irritable bowel syndrome is characterized by constipation, diarrhea, and abdominal pain and bloating. To control these symptoms doctors recommend staying away from dairy and fatty foods while including a high intake of fibre in your diet.

Avert hemorrhoids

Hemorrhoids are a swollen vein in the anal canal and while not life threatening, these veins can be very painful. They are caused by too much pressure in the pelvic and rectal areas. Part and parcel with controlling constipation, fibre can prevent you from straining too much when going to the bathroom and thereby help alleviate hemorrhoids.

Control your weight

Many health problems are associated with being overweight, among them heart disease, stroke, high blood pressure, type 2 diabetes and sleep apnea. To manage your weight and improve your overall health, doctors recommend a diet rich in fibre. Foods high in fibre will fill you up without costing you too many calories.

Detoxify your liver

We're constantly consuming toxins, whether it is from drinks or food, and your liver is responsible for clearing these toxins out of your body. Many doctors are skeptical of fad detox diets, saying they have the potential to do more harm than good. Luckily, one of the best and easiest things you can eat to help detoxify your liver is fruits like apples.

Boost your immune system

Red apples contain an antioxidant called quercetin. Recent studies have found that quercetin can help boost and fortify your immune system, especially when you're stressed out.

Turmeric

Turmeric or **tumeric** (*Curcuma longa*) is a rhizomatous herbaceous perennia plant of the ginger family, Zingiberaceae.

According to the Journal of the American Chemical Society, turmeric contains a wide range of antioxidant, antiviral, antibacterial, antifungal, anticarcinogenic, antimutagenic and anti-inflammatory properties. It is also loaded with many healthy nutrients such as protein, dietary fiber, niacin, Vitamin C, Vitamin E, Vitamin K, potassium, calcium, copper, iron, magnesium and zinc. Due to all these factors, turmeric is often used to treat a wide variety of health problems.

Processing:

Boiling: -

- a) Cleaned fresh rhizomes are kept in tin pan.
- b) While boiling, the water level should be 5-7 cm above the rhizomes.
- c) For quick and proper boiling, the rhizomes are covered with turmeric leaves 5-7 cm in thickness and plastered with mud and cow dung.
- d) Due to use of cow dung, fingers get artificially coloured with lead chromate (chemichrome) which is poisonous. To avoid this CFTRI, Mysore has

proposed to boil rhizomes in lime water (20 g Na₂CO₃ + 20 ml HCl per 50 kg rhizomes).

- e) Boiling is continued for about 1.5 hour.
- f) The rhizomes are boiled in water till froth comes out and white fumes appear giving out a characteristic odour.
- g) To test proper cooking a matchstick is pierced through the boiled rhizomes. If it passes easily through the rhizomes, the material is said to be cooked.
- h) Over cooking spoils the colour and fingers become light and get broken during polishing.

Drying

Rhizomes after cooking are stored in a heaps for overnight and then spread over a hard and clean ground.

- a) Drying is carried out for 8-15 days
- b) The material is stirred 2-3 times to ensure uniform drying.
- c) Improper drying results in the rhizomes become hard or brittle.
- d) The rounds and fingers are marketed. Few. bulbs, are sold as most of them are used for planting

Sorting

- a) Mother rhizomes and fingers if cooked together are separated before polishing.

- b) In Maharashtra only fingers are marketed. Few bulbs are sold as most of them are used for planting.

Polishing

Boiled and dried turmeric has rough and hard outer surface. Therefore they need to be polished before marketing.

Methods of polishing:

- a) Rubbing against hard surface or trampling under feet after wrapping in gunny bags.

b) Polishing Drum:

- * Used in Maharashtra.
- * Manually operated

- * Capacity, 20-30 kg per rotation,
- * Turmeric polished by smooth end has better colours and quality.

Uses of turmeric:

Prevents Cance

Turmeric can cancer, stop prostate destroy researchers active turmeric protectors induced preventive cells such as carcinomas carcinomas.

help prevent prostate the growth of existing cancer and even cancer cells. Multiple have found that the components in make it one of the best against radiation-tumors. It also has a effect against tumor T-cell leukemia, colon and breast

Relieves

Normal

Rheumatoid Arthritis **Arthritis**

The anti-inflammatory properties in turmeric are great for treating both osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. In addition, turmeric's antioxidant property destroys free radicals in the body that damage body cells. It has been found that those suffering from rheumatoid

arthritis who consumes turmeric on a regular basis experience much relief from the moderate to mild joint pains as well as joint inflammation.

Controls Diabetes

Turmeric can be used in the treatment of diabetes by helping to moderate insulin levels. It also improves glucose control and increases the effect of medications used to treat diabetes. Another significant benefit is turmeric's effectiveness in helping reduce insulin resistance, which may prevent the onset of Type-2 diabetes. However, when combined with strong medications, turmeric can cause hypoglycemia (low blood sugar). It is best to consult a healthcare professional before taking turmeric capsules.

Reduces Cholesterol Level

Research has proven that simply using turmeric as a food seasoning can reduce serum cholesterol levels. It is a known fact that high cholesterol can lead to other serious health problems. Maintaining a proper cholesterol level can prevent many cardiovascular diseases.

Immunity Booster

Turmeric contains a substance known as lipopolysaccharide, which helps stimulate the body's immune system. Its antibacterial, antiviral and antifungal agents also help strengthen the immune system. A strong immune system lessens the chance of suffering from colds, flu and coughs. If you do get a cold, a cough or the flu, you can feel better sooner by mixing one teaspoon of turmeric powder in a glass of warm milk and drinking it once daily.

Weight Management

Turmeric powder can be very helpful in maintaining an ideal body weight. A component present in turmeric helps increase the flow of bile, an important component in the breakdown of dietary fat. Those who wish to lose weight or treat obesity and other associated diseases can benefit from having one teaspoon of turmeric powder with every meal.

Prevents Alzheimer's Disease

Brain inflammation is suspected to be one of the leading causes of cognitive disorders such as Alzheimer's disease. Turmeric supports overall brain health by aiding in the removal of plaque build-up in the brain and improving the flow of oxygen. This can also prevent or slow down the progression of Alzheimer's disease.

Improves Digestion

Many key components in turmeric stimulate the gallbladder to produce bile, which then improves digestion and reduces symptoms of bloating and gas. Also, turmeric is helpful in treating most forms of inflammatory bowel disease including ulcerative colitis. However it is important to bear in mind that people suffering from any kind of gallbladder disease should not take turmeric as a dietary supplement as it may worsen the condition. It is best to consume turmeric in raw form when suffering from a digestive problem.

Prevents Liver Disease

Turmeric is a kind of natural liver detoxifier. The liver detoxifies the blood through the production of enzymes and turmeric increases production of these vital enzymes. These vital enzymes break down and reduce toxins in the body. Turmeric also is believed to invigorate and improve blood circulation. All of these factors support good liver health. Given the numerous health benefits of turmeric, adding this powerful herb to your diet is one of the best things you can do to improve the quality of your life. You can add turmeric in powder form to curries, stir fried dishes, smoothies, warm milk and even to spicy salad dressings. Turmeric can be taken in pill form also. However, turmeric should not be used by people with gallstones or bile obstruction.

References:

- 1) Barnes PM, Powell-Griner E, McFann K, Nahin RL. Complementary and alternative medicine use among adults: United States, 2002. *Adv Data*. 2004;343:1–19.
- 2) Swerdlow JL. Modern Science Embraces Medicinal Plants. *Nature's Medicine: Plants that Heal*. Washington, DC: National Geographic Society; 2000. pp. 110–57.
- 3) Barrett B, Kiefer D, Rabago D. Assessing the risks and benefits of herbal medicine: an overview of scientific evidence. *Altern Ther Health Med*. 1999;5:40–9.
- 4) Rotblatt M, Ziment I. Evidence-based herbal medicine. Philadelphia, PA: Hanley & Belfus; 2002.
- 4) Ernst E. Herbal Medicine in the Treatment of Rheumatic Diseases. *Rheumatic Diseases Clinics of North America*. 2011;37(1).
- 5) Ke F, Yadav PK, Ju LZ. Herbal medicine in the treatment of ulcerative colitis. *Saudi J Gastroenterol*. 2012;18(1):3-10
- 6) Agrawal S (2007) *Herbal Drug technology*, Universities press (India) Private Limited, Hyderabad, India 1.
Dhiman AK (2004) *Common Drug Plants and Ayurvedic Remedies*. (1stedn), Reference Press, New Delhi, India 286-287.
- 7) Adaramoye O. A, Medeiros I. A. 2008. Involvement of Na(+)-Ca (2+) exchanger in .the endothelium- independent vasorelaxation induced by *Curcuma longa* L. in isolated rat superior mesenteric arteries *J Smooth Muscle Res* 2008 44(5):151 8.
- 8) Arora R. B, Kapoor V, Basu N, Jain A. P. Anti-inflammatory studies on
- 10) *Curcuma longa* (turmeric) *Indian J Med Res*. 1971;59:1289–95.
- 11) "An apple a day keeps the doctor away". vegparadise.com. Archived from the original on 11 February 2008. Retrieved 27 January 2008.